

Research Article

Acute Urinary Retention and Delirium in End-of-Life Cancer Patients

*Corresponding author

Miguel Borregón, Medical Oncology Service, Hospital General Universitario de Elda, Spain

Received: 27 Mar 2022

Accepted: 01 Apr 2022

Published: 13 Apr 2022

Copyright

© 2022 Miguel Borregón

OPEN ACCESS

Miguel Borregón^{1*}, Katherine Martínez², Alba Ramos³, Irene Ramos³, Beatriz Berzal³, Manuel Mazariegos³, Margarita Díez³, Cristina Gómez³, Ana Belén Rupérez³, Irene Otero³, Ana Karina Santos³, Juan David Cárdenas³, Elia Martínez⁴, HC Liu⁵, Elizabeth Gutiérrez⁶, María Victoria Baeza⁶ and Inmaculada Raja⁶

¹Medical Oncology Service, Hospital General Universitario de Elda, Spain

²Medical Oncology Service, Hospital General de Segovia, Spain

³Medical Oncology Service, Hospital Virgen de la Salud de Toledo, Spain

⁴Medical Oncology Service, Hospital Universitario de Fuenlabrada, Spain

⁵La Jolla Center for Precision Radiation Medicine, California, USA

⁶Palliative Care Service, Hospital Virgen de la Salud de Toledo, Spain

Abstract

Symptom control at end-of-life (EOL) is one of the key goals for oncologists and palliative care doctors. Acute urinary retention (AUR) is a common problem at EOL, leading to patient discomfort and delirium development. Once identified, the treatment for AUR is quick, simple and comforting. We conducted a retrospective and descriptive study in a cancer Palliative Care Unit (PCU). 33.3% of patients at EOL experienced AUR. Their mean age was 78.8 years and 69.2% were males. 61.5% presented palpable distended bladder and their mean survival from bladder catheterisation to death was 3.1 days. 100% patients were being treated with butylscopolamine, 46.1% presented with lung cancer, 92.3% presented with distant metastases, and 15.4% had previously presented with AUR. 53.8% were suffering delirium at AUR diagnosis, and 71.4% resolved their delirium after bladder catheterisation. Improving recognition of symptoms and its causes in the PCU setting will result in patient relief and comfort.

Key words: End-of- life (EOL), Acute urine retention (AUR), Palpable distended bladder, Delirium

Introduction

Symptom control at end-of-life (EOL) is one of the key goals for oncologists and palliative care doctors [1]. Different distressing symptoms often coexist in this setting, which introduces difficulty in discerning an underlying cause. These symptoms usually alter patient's overall well-being. Acute urinary retention (AUR) is a common problem at EOL and is influenced by the individual patient, the disease and various medication factors [2,3]. Many drug, such as benzodiazepines, opioids, anticholinergics and antidepressants, prescribed for EOL patients are known to alter bladder function and can influence the onset of AUR [4]. AUR can lead to patient discomfort and delirium development. Once identified, the treatment for AUR is quick, simple and comforting. Clinical trials and literature about this topic remain scarce. Given the significant burden of illness and care associated with AUR in EOL cancer patients, our team conducted a study focusing on its epidemiology and relation with delirium.

Methods

Retrospective and descriptive study executed in the Palliative Care Unit (PCU) of the Hospital Virgen de la Salud de Toledo, Spain. This unit cares for oncology patients at the EOL when hospital admission is deemed necessary. Patient medical history was collected retrospectively (between January and February 2018) from the electronic medical records. Patients in EOL condition were defined as patients who presented to hospital admis-

sion with the event that ultimately caused the patient's death. Patients who did not present EOL were excluded. AUR was defined as the inability to voluntarily urinate as described by the patient, their relatives or the medical staff and requiring bladder catheterization. AUR epidemiology, clinical features and relationship with delirium is described in the following paragraphs. This study was approved by Hospital Virgen de la Salud de Toledo sciences research ethics board.

Results

The data collection period of the study was 2 months (59 days). There were 51 new patients admitted in PCU at this time, all of which had a cancer diagnosis. The 51 admissions accounted for a total of 48 patients, 3 of which were readmissions (5.9%). Thirty-nine patients (76.4%) presented with the defined EOL condition. 13 of these patients experienced AUR (33.3%). Of the patients that experienced AUR, 9 were male (69.2%) and 4 were female (30.8%). Of the patients that did not experience AUR, 18 were male (69.2%) and 8 (30.8%) were female. The mean age of patients presenting with AUR was 78.8 years, compared with 71.5 years in patients not presenting AUR. The mean number of days from admission to death in patients presenting with AUR was 10.2 days, compared to 10.3 days in patients not presenting with AUR. This epidemiologic data is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Patient's Epidemiology

EPIDEMIOLOGY	PATIENTS EOL PRESENTING AUR: 13 (33.3%)	PACIENTS EOL NOT PRESENTING AUR: 26 (66.6%)
Patients admitted in PCU: 51	/	/
Patients presenting PCU readmission: 3 (5,9%)	/	/
Patients presenting EOL: 39 (76,4%)	13 (33.3%)	26 (66.6%)
Gender (males)	9 (69,2%)	18 (69,2%)
Mean age	78,8 (94 - 57)	71,5 (100 - 26)
Days of in-hospital to death	10,2 (25 - 3)	10,3 (32 - 1)

*EOL: end-of-life situation.

*AUR: acute urinary retention.

Of the 13 patients that experienced AUR, 6 (46.1%) were diagnosed with lung cancer (3 lung adenocarcinoma and 3 epidermoid lung cancer), 2 (15.4%) were diagnosed with kidney cancer, 2 (15.4%) were diagnosed with colorectal cancer, 1 (7.7%) was diagnosed with prostate cancer, 1 (7.7%) was diagnosed with head and neck cancer (eyelid carcinoma), and 1 patient (7.7%) was diagnosed with two concomitant cancers: tricholeukemia and bladder cancer. The tumor related data is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Tumor Sites

TUMOR	PATIENTS EOL PRESENTING AUR: 13 (33.3%)	PACIENTS EOL NOT PRESENTING AUR: 26 (66.6%)
Lung cancer	6 (46.1%)	8 (30.8%)
Colorectal cancer	2 (15.4%)	6 (23%)
Kidney cancer	2 (15.4%)	3 (11.5%)
Head and neck cancer	1 (7.7%)	3 (11.5%)
Blood cancer	1 (7.7%)	1 (3.8%)
Prostate cancer	1 (7.7%)	2 (7.7%)
Bladder cancer	1 (7.7%)	0
Pancreatic or liver cancer	0	3 (11.5%)
Stomach cancer	0	1 (3.8%)
Brain cancer	0	1 (3.8%)
Melanoma	0	1 (3.8%)
Breast cancer	0	1 (3.8%)
2 tumors at the same time	1 (7.7%)	4 (15.4%)
Distance metastases	12 (92.3%)	17 (65.4%)

*EOL: end-of-life situation.

*AUR: acute urinary retention.

Regarding physical examination among patients who experienced AUR, 8 (61.5%) patients presented palpable distended bladder, 4 (30.8%) patients were unclear for this finding, and 1 (7.7%) patient did not present palpable distended bladder. Among the 8 patients that presented with a palpable

distended bladder on physical examination, the mean volume of urine at the time of bladder catheterisation was 536 cc. Their mean survival from bladder catheterisation to death was 3.1 days. This AUR related data is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: AUR Features

AUR FEATURES	PATIENTS EOL PRESENTING AUR: 13 (33.3%)
Experienced delirium	7 (53.8%)
Delirium resolved after bladder catheterisation	5 (71.4%)
Palpable distended bladder: Yes / unclear / No	8 (61.5%) / 4 (30.8%) / 1 (7.7%)
Mean volume of urine (cc)	536 (1100 - 300)
On treatment with butylscopolamine	13 (100%)
Previous AUR	2 (15.4%)
Mean survival after bladder catheterisation (days)	3,1 (8 - 1)

*EOL: end-of-life situation.

*AUR: acute urinary retention.

Regarding risk factors involved in AUR development, 13 (100%) patients who experienced AUR were being treated with butylscopolamine for symptoms relief. Information regarding other common drugs prescribed in EOL that could also contribute to AUR onset was not collected. Of patients that experienced AUR, 6 (46.1%) presented with lung cancer, compared with 8 (30.8%) patients that not experienced AUR. In contrast, digestive tract tumors were less frequent in the AUR group. Of patients that experienced AUR, 12 (92.3%) patients presented with distant metastases, compared with 17 (65.4%) patients that not experienced AUR. In the AUR group, only 2 (15.4%) patients had previously presented with AUR during their hospital admission.

Regarding the development of delirium, 7 (53.8%) patients who experienced AUR were suffering delirium at AUR diagnosis and prior to bladder catheterisation. Five (71.4%) of these patients resolved their delirium after bladder catheterisation and urine excretion. Delirium development was not collected in patients who did not experienced AUR.

Discussion

No other published studies have, to our knowledge, described and compared the relationship between AUR and delirium in the palliative care setting.

In our study, the incidence of AUR, defined as the inability to voluntarily urinate as described by the patient, their relatives or the medical staff and requiring bladder catheterization, was 33.3%. Patients who experienced AUR were older compared to patients who did not experienced AUR. There was no association found between AUR and sex or between AUR and length of hospital admission.

The prevalence of bladder catheterization in PCU patients was first described by Fainsinger, et al. with a 72% incidence rate [5]. Gutmanis, et al. described an incidence rate of 57.5% and found that 69% patients presented with a performance status of 30% or less when bladder catheterization was performed. They also described the reasons for this catheterization, finding that the indication was AUR in 81% patients, energy conservation in 7.1%, and urinary tract infection in 4.8%. The mean volume of urine at the time of catheter insertion was 561.7 cc for males and 657.4 cc for females [6].

Our study shows that physical examination was highly suggestive for AUR, finding a palpable distended bladder in most cases. Among patients presenting palpable distended bladder on physical examination, mean volume of urine at the time of catheterisation was more than 500 cc. Survival after bladder catheterisation was limited, indicating that AUR presents soon before the patient's death.

In our study, the risk factors for the development of AUR are as follows: advanced age, butylscopolamine prescription, previous AUR episodes, lung cancer and presence of distant metastases.

Some studies have addressed the relation between polypharmacy and AUR. Currow, et al. described that the average number of prescribed medications in the days preceding death among patients admitted in a PCU was 7 [7]. Sera et al. described that among cancer patients admitted to hospice, almost all patients received an opioid analgesic, and the majority received anticholinergics, benzodiazepines and antidopaminergics [8]. Bergstra, et al. focused their study on the medication prescription associated with AUR in a retrospective case-control trial in a PCU in Ontario, Canada. This study did not show that the addition of different classes of retention-causing medications increases the risk for AUR. Antidopaminergic medications were the only medication that showed statistically significant differences between patients who were catheterized for AUR and

those who were not catheterized (85.3% versus 61.3%). The current proposed hypothesis is that AUR might be a physiological phenomenon that is inherent to the dying process for some people, especially those with very deteriorated performance status [9]. Agar et al. described the side effects of anticholinergic load in the palliative care setting. They found that anticholinergic load rose as death approached due to increasing use of medications for symptom control. Symptoms significantly associated were dry mouth, difficulty concentrating and decreasing performance status [10].

In our study, delirium rates in AUR patients were high, with over 50% of AUR patients experiencing delirium. In most cases, delirium was resolved after bladder catheterization.

Delirium is characterized by a disturbance of consciousness, cognition, and perception, with fluctuating course and sudden start. Its consequences are distressing for the patient, destructive for the family and frustrating for the medical team. Sometimes it is possible to find a relation between delirium episode and drugs, metabolic disturbances, or the cancer itself. Almost 50% of delirium episodes are reversible as shown in recent prospective studies. Delirium is under treated and poorly identified in many terminal cancer patients; however, it is possible to improve its recognition if strict patient assessment is performed. AUR is an important condition to assess bedside at the onset of delirium [11,12].

The small sample size and the study design as a single-centre, retrospective study are notable limitations. Other limitations of the study include the examination of butylscopolamine as the only class of retention-causing medications. There was also a lack of data regarding delirium development in patients not suffering AUR.

Conclusion

This study deeply describes AUR epidemiology, clinical features and relation with delirium in oncology patients at EOL. AUR is found to be a common problem at EOL, and its routine screening among patients suffering delirium in the PCU setting is mandatory. AUR identification by physical examination is easy, and its treatment is simple and resolves patient complaint in most of cases. Training and improving recognition of symptoms and its causes in the palliative care setting by nurses and physicians will result in patient relief and comfort—the main goals in EOL condition.

Disclosure Statement

The authors of this article declare that there is no conflict of interest with respect to its publication. All the authors have participated in the study and have read and approved the manuscript. Likewise, we assume all the responsibility about its contents.

Funding Source

The authors of this article declare that there is no funding source for this study other than the base salary derived from the work in the public Spanish health system of its participants.

Acknowledgements

The authors of this manuscript thank all of the patients and their families on the PCU of Hospital Virgen de la Salud de Toledo.

We also would like to acknowledge to Dr. José Ignacio Chacón, Medical Oncologist of Medical Oncology Department in Hospital Virgen de la Salud, his contribution on the education of new oncologist residents. He has always been open to help and guide clinical and researching projects.

We also would like to acknowledge to Palliative care Service in Hospital Virgen de la Salud de Toledo, Spain, their important daily labour to care cancer patients. Their work offers light to patients and family.

References

1. Singer PA, Martin DK, Kelner M (1999) Quality end-of-life care: patients' perspectives. *JAMA* 281: 163-168.
2. Lichter I, Hunt E (1990) The last 48 hours of life. *J Palliat Care* 6: 7-15.
3. Hui D, dos Santos R, Chisholm GB, Bruera E (2015) Symptom Expression in the Last Seven Days of Life Among Cancer Patients Admitted to Acute Palliative Care Units. *J Pain Symptom Manage* 50: 488-494.
4. Verhamme KM, Sturkenboom MC, Stricker BH, Bosch R (2008) Drug-induced urinary retention: incidence, management and prevention. *Drug Saf* 31: 373-388.
5. Fainsinger RL, MacEachern T, Hanson J, Bruera E (1992) The use of urinary catheters in terminally ill cancer patients. *J Pain Symptom Manage* 7: 333-338.
6. Gutmanis I, Shadd J, Woolmore-Goodwin S, Whitfield P, Byrne J, et al. (2014) Prevalence and indications for bladder catheterization on a palliative care unit: a prospective, observational study. *Palliat Med* 28: 1239-1240.
7. Currow DC, Stevenson JP, Abernethy AP, Plummer J, Shelby-James TM (2007) Prescribing in palliative care as death approaches. *J Am Geriatr Soc* 55: 590-595.
8. Sera L, McPherson ML, Holmes HM (2014) Commonly prescribed medications in a population of hospice patients. *Am J Hosp Palliat Care* 31: 126-131.
9. Bergstra TG, Gutmanis I, Byrne J, et al. (2017) Urinary Retention and Medication Utilization on a Palliative Care Unit: A Retrospective Observational Study. *J Pain Palliat Care Pharmacother* 31: 212-217.
10. Agar M, Currow D, Plummer J, Seidel R, Carnahan R, et al. (2009) Changes in anticholinergic load from regular prescribed medications in palliative care as death approaches. *Palliat Med* 23: 257-265.
11. Cobb JL, Glantz MJ, Nicholas PK, et al. (2000) Delirium in patients with cancer at the end of life. *Cancer Pract* 8: 172-177.
12. Centeno C, Vara F, Pérez P, Sanz A, Bruera E (2003) Presentación clínica e identificación del delirium en el cáncer avanzado. *Med Pal* 10: 24-35.

Cite this article: Miguel Borregón, Katherine Martínez, Alba Ramos, Irene Ramos, Beatriz Berzal, et al. (2022) Acute Urinary Retention and Delirium in End-of-Life Cancer Patients. *Archives of Clinical Case Studies and Case Reports* 3(3): 298- 301.

Copyright: ©2022 **Miguel Borregón**. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.